

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW ON VISPHOṬA W.S.R TO AYURVEDIC ETIOPATHOGENESIS AND MANAGEMENT

Priyanka J. Havalad*¹, Nataraj H. R.², Shakthi Rani S. N.³

^{1,3}PG Scholar Department of Agada Tantra Sri Dharmasthala Manjunateshwara college of Ayurveda and Hospital Hassan.

²Associate Professor Department of Agada Tantra Sri Dharmasthala Manjunateshwara College of Ayurveda and Hospital Hassan.

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*Corresponding Author

Priyanka J. Havalad

PG Scholar Department of Agada
Tantra Sri Dharmasthala
Manjunateshwara college of Ayurveda
and Hospital Hassan.

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ABSTRACT

Visphoṭa is a *Pitta–Rakta* predominant *Kṣudra Roga* characterized by vesicular eruptions resembling burns, often associated with fever, burning sensation, pain, and pruritus. Classical *Ayurvedic* texts describe *Visphoṭa* in detail under *Kuṣṭha* and *Kṣudra Roga*, highlighting its etiopathogenesis, clinical varieties, prognosis, and therapeutic principles. This article aims to systematically present the *Nidana*, *Samprapti*, *Lakṣaṇa*, *Upadrava*, *Sadhya–Asadhya*, and *Cikitsa* of *Visphoṭa* based on classical references, and to correlate it with modern dermatological conditions such as pemphigus vulgaris. The review emphasizes *Ayurvedic* management strategies including *Sodhana*, *Samana*, *Pathya–Apathya*, and external therapies, demonstrating their clinical relevance in contemporary practice.

KEYWORDS: *Visphoṭa*, *Visphoṭaka*, *Pitta–Rakta*, *Kṣudra*

Roga, Pemphigus vulgaris.

INTRODUCTION

Skin disorders have been elaborately described in *Ayurveda* due to their visibility, chronicity, and impact on quality of life. *Visphoṭa*, also known as *Visphoṭaka*, is described as a vesiculobullous disorder primarily caused by vitiation of *Pitta* and *Rakta*. Classical texts compare its lesions to burns produced by fire, indicating severe inflammatory pathology.

Visphoṭa is discussed under *Kuṣṭha Cikitsa* and *Kṣudra Roga Pratiśedha* in texts such as *Charaka Samhita*, *Sushruta Samhita*, *Ashtanga Hridaya*, and *Bhavaprakasha*. In modern medicine, *Visphoṭa* closely resembles autoimmune blistering disorders such as pemphigus vulgaris. Understanding *Visphoṭa* through both classical and contemporary lenses aids in holistic disease management.^[1]

Pemphigus vulgaris is a severe, debilitating autoimmune skin disorder that significantly impairs quality of life and carries a mortality rate of approximately 5–15%. It is characterized by fragile blisters and erosions affecting the skin and mucous membranes, caused by intraepithelial acantholysis. The disease occurs due to IgG autoantibodies targeting desmoglein-3, a key adhesion molecule in desmosomes, leading to loss of cell-to-cell cohesion. Lesions typically present as thin-walled bullae that rupture easily, leaving painful, non-healing erosions. Pemphigus vulgaris commonly affects individuals in the fifth and sixth decades of life, with genetic, environmental, and ethnic predispositions, and is associated with considerable physical and psychological stress.^[2]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This article is a classical literature-based review derived from:

- *Ayurvedic Saṃhitas* and *Nighaṅṭus*
- Authoritative Texts like *Bhaiṣajya Ratnavali* and *Madhava Nidana*.

Acc to (*Su.ni*)^[3]

Sphota (vesicle) resembling those produced by burning fire accompanied fever produced by *pitta* and *rakta*, seen either at any one place or the body is known as *Visphotaka*.

Acc to [*cha.chi*]^[4]

Colour - *Shweta Aruna Bhasa* (white reddish in appearance) Nature - *Visphota* (eruptions) and *Tanutwacha* (thin skin)

It occurs due to *Pitta* and *Kapha Dosha*.

Acc to [*AH*]^[5]

Sphoṭa (vesicles, blebs) more difficult to bear than *masurika*, having severe pain is known as *Visphota*.

Nidana Acc to (Bha.pra)^[6]

Excessive intake of:

- *Kaṭu, Amla, Tikṣṇa, Uṣṇa, Vidahi, Rukṣha* foods
- *Kṣhara dravyas*
- *Ajirṇa, Adhyasana*
- *Atapa sevana* (excess sun exposure)

These lead to *Dosha prakopa*, especially *Pitta* and *Rakta*.

Samprapti (Pathogenesis)^[7]

Nidana Sevana

(Excess intake of *Kaṭu, Amla, Tikṣṇa, Uṣṇa, Vidahi, Rukṣha ahara; Ajirṇa, Adhyasana; Atapa sevana*)

Aggravation of *Doṣhas (Doṣha Prakopa)*

Predominant *Pitta* and *Rakta Doṣha*

Associated *Kapha* (causing *kandu, sthirata*) and *Vata* (causing *vedana, sula*)

Rakta Duṣṭi

Vitiation of *Rakta* due to *Asrayasrayi bhava* with *Pitta*

Dhatu Duṣṭi

Involvement of

- *Rakta Dhatu – Daha, Raga, Sravana*
- *Mamsa Dhatu – Sphoṭa utpatti, sotha*
- *Asthi Dhatu – Gambhira vedana* in severe cases

Sthanasamsraya (Localization)

Doṣha–Duṣṭya saṁmurchana occurs in *Twak* (skin)

Agni–Srotas Duṣṭi

Impairment of *Bhrajaka Pitta* and *Rasavaha–Raktavaha srotas*

Jwara Utpatti

Systemic inflammatory response due to *Pitta–Rakta prakopa*

Visphoṭa

Formation of *Sphoṭa* (vesicles/bullae)

- Thin-walled (*Tanu twacha*)
- White-reddish or yellowish in color
- Resembling *Agnidagdha vrana* (burn injuries)

Clinical Manifestation

- *Daha* (burning sensation)
 - *Ruja* (pain)
 - *Kandu* (itching)
 - *Sravana* (oozing)
 - *Jwara* (fever)

Distribution of Lesions

- Localized *Visphoṭa* – involvement of limited areas
- Generalized *Visphoṭa* – spread over entire body surface

Samprapti Ghaṭaka

<i>Doṣha</i>	<i>Pitta (पित्त), Rakta; Kapha & Vata anubandha</i>
<i>Duṣya</i>	<i>Rakta, Maṃsa, Asthi</i>
<i>Srotas</i>	<i>Rasavaha, Raktavaha</i>
<i>Srotoduṣṭi</i>	<i>Saṅga, Vimargagamana</i>
<i>Agni</i>	<i>Jatharagni & Bhrajaka Pitta duṣṭi</i>
<i>Adhiṣṭhana</i>	<i>Tvak</i>
<i>Roga Marga</i>	<i>Bahya</i>
<i>Udbhava Sthana</i>	<i>Amasaya</i>
<i>Vyakti Sthana</i>	<i>Tvak</i>
<i>Svabhava</i>	<i>Asukari (acute)</i>

Lakṣhaṇas Acc to *Bha.Pra*^[8], *Madhava nidana*^[9], *Vangasena*^[10]

Doṣha Lakṣhaṇa

1. *Vataja* Severe pain, headache, joint pain, blackish discoloration
2. *Pittaja* Burning sensation, fever, suppuration, yellow-red vesicles
3. *Kaphaja* Itching, hardness, pallor, delayed suppuration
4. *Sannipataja* Depressed center, elevated margins, severe systemic symptoms; incurable

5. *Vatapittaja* – Severe pain

6. *Kaphapittaja* – itching, burning sensation, jwara, vomiting.

7. *Kaphavataja* – itching, stiffness, heavy.

Upadrava [Acc to *Bha.pra*]^[11]

- *Hikka* (hiccups)
- *Swasa* (dyspnea)
- *Aruchi*
- *Trushna*
- *Hṛdavyatha*
- *Angamarda*
- *Visarpa*
- Severe fever and nausea

Sadhya–Asadhya Acc to [*Bha.pra*]^[12]

- *Ekadoṣaja* – *Sadhya*
- *Dvidoṣaja* – *Kricchra Sadhya*
- *Tridoṣaja* with multiple *Upadravas* – *Asadhya*

Pathya Acc to (*Bha.pra*)^[13]

Old *Sali* rice, *Yava*, *Mudga*, *Masura*, *Aḍhaki*

Apathya Acc to (*Bha.pra*)

Uṣṇa, *Tikṣṇa*, *Guru*, *Vidahi* foods, exercise, anger, day sleep

CHIKITSA ACC TO (*Bha.Pra*)^[14]

- *Laṅghana*
- *Vamana* (when *Kapha* dominant)
- *Virechana* (*Pitta–Rakta* dominant)
- *Pathya ahara*

CHIKITSA ACC TO DOSHA Acc to (*Bha.pra*)^[15]

VATAJA	<i>kashaya</i> of the <i>pancamula</i> , <i>rasna</i> , <i>darvi</i> , <i>usira</i> , <i>duralabha</i> , <i>gudūci</i> , <i>dhanyaka</i> , and <i>musta</i> consumed, cures <i>visphoṭa</i> of <i>vata</i> origin.
PITTAJA	<i>kashaya</i> of <i>drakṣa</i> , <i>kaṣmarya</i> , <i>kharjura</i> , <i>patola</i> , <i>ariṣṭa</i> , <i>vasaka</i> , <i>kaṭuka</i> , <i>laja</i> added with <i>sita</i> (sugar) and consumed cures <i>visphoṭa</i> of <i>pitta</i> origin.
KAPHAJA	<i>kashaya</i> of <i>bhunimba</i> , <i>vaca</i> , <i>vasa</i> , <i>triphalā</i> , <i>indrayava</i> , <i>vatsaka</i> ,

	<i>picumarda</i> and <i>patola</i> added with honey cures <i>visphoṭa</i> of <i>kapha</i> origin.
ALL TYPES OF VISPHOTA	<i>kiratatikta</i> , <i>yaṣṭyahva</i> , <i>musta</i> , <i>vasaka</i> , <i>patola</i> , <i>parpaṭa</i> , <i>usira</i> , <i>nimba</i> , <i>indrayava</i> these twelve drugs made into <i>kashaya</i> and consumed cures all varieties of <i>visphota</i> .

CHIKITSA ACC TO (*Bhai.Ratna*)^[16]

- *Virechana*
- *Vamana*
- *Lepana*
- *Langhana*

LEPA PRAYOGAS ACC TO (*Bha.Pra*)^[17]

1. For the destruction of *Visphoṭa* disease, a person should prepare a paste (*lepa*) using the *kutaja beeja*, triturated with rice-washed water (*Tanduliyaka*) and apply it externally.
2. A paste prepared from sandalwood, *nagapushpa*, *sariva*, *taṇḍuliyaka*, and *siriṣa* is effective in alleviating burning sensation.
3. A paste made by grinding *utpala*, sandalwood, *lodhra*, *usira*, and both varieties of *sariva* with water destroys blisters, burning sensation, and the associated pain.

KASHAYA PRAYOGA ACC TO (*Bha.Pra*)^[18]

1. A decoction prepared from *Paṭola*, *amṛuta* (*Guduchi*), *Bhunimba*, *Vasaka*, *Ariṣṭaparpaṭa*, and *Khadira* alleviates the pain of *Visphoṭa* and reduces associated fever.
2. *Paṭola*, *Triphala*, *Ariṣṭa*, *Guduci*, *Musta*, *Candana*, *moorva*, *Rohiṇi*, *Paṭha*, *Rajani*, and *duralabha*—this decoction should be administered orally.
3. This decoction alleviates fever arising from *Pitta and Kapha*, and destroys itching, skin disorders, *Visphoṭa*, poison-related conditions, and *Visarpa*.

Siriṣamooladikavalagraha Acc to (*Chakra datta*)

The roots of *Siriṣa*, *Manjiṣṭha*, *Cavya*, *Amalaka*, and *Yaṣṭika*, along with tender leaves of *Jati* and honey, are used as a gargle (*kavala-graha*) in *Visphoṭa*.

TRIPHALADI YOGA – Acc to (*Cha.chi*)^[19]

Ingredients- *Triphala*, *Patola Patra*, *Katurohini*, *Nimba*, *Asahara*, *Trayamana*, *Masura*, *Vidala*, *Ghrta*.

Indications- It is useful in *Vata Pittaja Kushta*, *Visarpa*, *Vatarakta*, *Jwara*, *Daha*, *Gulma*, *Vidradhi*, *Bhrama* (*giddiness*) and *Visphotaka*.

Mahatiktaka Ghrita Acc to (Cha.chi)^[20]

Ingredients - Pippali, Padmaka, Haridra, Daruharidra, Sadgrantha, Vishala, Satavari, Sariva Bedha (Krishna and Shweta), Vatsaka Beeja, Vasa, Murva, Amruta, Kiratatikta, Yastimadhu and Trayamana.

Indication: *Visphotaka*.

Pancha Tikta Ghritam Acc to (Bha.pra)^[21]

Ingredients: *Murcchita ghritam, patola, saptacchada, nimba (heart wood), triphala and cinnaruha.*

Indication: *Sannipatika visphota*

Dasanga lepa Acc to Vangasena^[22]

Sirisa, madhuyasti, tagara, candana, ela, mamsi, haridra, daruharidra, kustha and balaka (total ten drugs) and mixed with ghrita alleviates Visphota and itching.

Kashayas prayogas^[23]

- *Triphaladi kashya*
- *Patolakaturohinyadi kashaya*
- *Laghu manjista kashya* (used in skin diseases produced due to vitiation of *rakta*)
- *Mahamanjistadi Kashaya*
- *Rasnasaptaka Kashaya*
- *Panchavalkala kwatha* for external wash.

Asava and Aristas

- *Kumariyasava*
- *Usirasava*
- *Vidangarista*
- *kadirarista*

Choorna prayoga

- *Pancha Nimba choorna*
- *Satavari choorna*
- *Navayasa choorna*

Ghrita prayoga

- *Amrutha ghrita*
- *Mahatiktaka ghrita*
- *Kasisadya ghrita* (external application)
- *Shatadoutha ghrita*
- *Jatyadi ghrita*

Taila prayoga

- *Satavari taila*
- *Marichadi taila*
- *Triphaladi taila*
- *Jatyadi taila*
- *Chandanadi taila*
- *Vacha taila*
- *Pinda taila*

Shamana Yogas

- ***Kvātha:*** *Triphaladi, Patola–Katurohiṇyadi, Mahamanjiṣṭhadi*
- ***Ghṛta:*** *Mahatiktaka Ghṛta, Pancatikta Ghṛta*
- ***Lepa:*** *Dasaṅga Lepa, Kuṭaja bija lepa*
- ***Taila:*** *Kampillakādi Taila*
- ***Asava–Ariṣṭa:*** *Kumaryasava, Usirasava*

A Case study was done on Ayurvedic Management of Visphotaka^[24]

Presenting Complaints: A six years old male patient complaints of generalized vesicle type lesion with sever burning sensation associated with mild itching and fever and oozing (most affected area were upper extremities, face, trunk and upper part of the back side) since last 3 months.

The Following Treatment was given

Name of the drugs	Dose and time of administration	Anupana	Duration (28-08-2018 to 12-9-2018)
Mahatikta ghreeta	5ml in empty stomach at morning approx. 6-6.30am	Luke warm water	15 days
Trivrit avaleham	1 TSF 6gm at night after meal.	Luke warm water	15 days.
Kasaya dhara (pouring of medicated decoction over the body)	(Approximate 2 lit one time) two-time daily morning and evening	-	15 days

2nd phage of management- Shamana- the patient was discharged with internal medication which was continued for two and half months, showed in table no-2.

Table 2: 2nd phage of management- Shamana

Name of medicine	Dose and time of administration	Anupan	Duration
Avipattikar Churna	2.5gm twice in a day before meal	Luke warm milk	(13-9-2018 to 27-11-2018)
Sarivadyasavam	10ml thrice daily after meal -lunch & dinner	Luke warm water	(13-9-2018 to 27-11-2018)
Navayas lauha + Punarnabadi mandur + Motipisti	250mg + 250mg +125mg mixed together with honey taken two times daily before food- morning and evening.	Luke warm water	(13-9-2018 to 27-11-2018)

Before Treatment

Figure-1

Figure-2

Figure-3

After Treatment

Figure-4

Figure-5

Figure-6

RESULT

- Fever was subsided; burning sensation, pruritus and pain was massively reduced; ruptured bullae of affected area of skin started to peel off which was seen during the 2nd outpatient (45 days from 1st visit) door visit.
- After one and half months from 2nd visit level management bullae were started to replace by normal skin with scarring and hyper pigmentation along with complete remission of burning sensation, pain, oozing, fever and pruritus.

DISCUSSION

Visphoṭa represents an acute inflammatory blistering pathology rooted in Pitta–Rakta duṣṭi. The resemblance of *Visphoṭa* lesions to burns (*agnidagdha iva sphoṭaḥ*) indicates severe *Ushna and Tikṣṇa guṇa* dominance. Classical descriptions align remarkably with modern autoimmune vesiculobullous disorders, especially pemphigus vulgaris.

Ayurvedic management emphasizes early *Doṣha samana* and *Rakta prasadana*, which may explain the favorable outcomes observed in reported cases. Unlike modern management relying heavily on long-term corticosteroids and immunosuppressants, *Ayurveda* adopts a multi-modal approach addressing digestion, immunity, tissue nourishment, and local healing. This holistic strategy may reduce complications, recurrence, and drug dependency.

CONCLUSION

Visphoṭa is a *Pitta–Rakta* predominant dermatological disorder characterized by vesicular eruptions, burning sensation, and systemic involvement. Classical Ayurvedic literature provides a comprehensive framework for understanding its etiology, pathogenesis, and management. Early diagnosis, appropriate *sodhana* and *Samana* therapies, strict adherence to *Pathya–Apathya*, and external applications play a crucial role in disease control. Integrating Ayurvedic principles in managing vesiculobullous disorders offers a safe, effective, and holistic alternative, especially in chronic and recurrent cases.

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